

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND LIFE CONCEPTS IN THE PSYCHE OF A CHILD

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ABSTRACT

In this article, a number of problematic issues and general opinions on the formation and development of scientific and life concepts in the child's psyche are described.

Every country is on the path of historical development, rapid development of the country, achievement of certain achievements, well-being of the people depends on the level of attention paid to the education and future of the youth of this country. Therefore, the issue of youth in Uzbekistan is considered one of the most important directions in the policy of our country. A solid legal framework has been created to protect the rights and interests of young people, to create the necessary conditions and opportunities, and this system is currently being improved in accordance with the requirements of the times. The development of the child's psyche is a very complex and contradictory process, as in any other development, where quantitative changes lead to qualitative changes, transitions, "jumps". For example, the gradual increase in the vocabulary of a child leads to the acquisition of the grammatical structure of the language, and the repetition of certain actions and behaviors many times results in the formation of certain skills, habits, and fixed characteristics in a person. According to the most general laws of the development of the child's psyche, firstly, the integration of consistency, that is, the integration of the initial scattered mental states of the child into the stable mental characteristics of the person, individual views of certain events into a unified worldview; secondly, the uneven development of certain processes, functions and characteristics of the child's personality; thirdly, it is possible to introduce plasticity, which ensures that certain functional deficiencies are filled with other functions (compensation).

The integration of the child's psyche, for example, is clearly manifested in the formation of observability based on the complete perception of individual objects and events, and diligence based on the fulfillment of certain labor tasks with love. Unevenness of mental development can occur in all periods of life. For example, in preschool age, especially speech, interest in learning and logical (logical) thinking, etc., develop rapidly in adolescence. Mental

development of a child is the improvement of the processes and characteristics of a person, as well as the formation of new, higher qualities and characteristics based on them. The development of the psyche takes place under the decisive influence of the social environment and education in the process of personal activity, that is, in the process of the child's activity.

Concepts are one of the main components of the content of any educational subject, including elementary school subjects. One of the first mathematical concepts a child encounters in school is the concept of number. If this concept is not sufficiently mastered, students will have serious difficulties in further movement in the number system, including in understanding the concept of the number system. Primary school students come across different concepts in acquiring scientific knowledge. Students inability to distinguish concepts leads to their insufficient mastery. The task of the teacher is to ensure the full mastery of these concepts.

Concepts appear to students as elements of social experience. They record the achievements of previous generations. Students should turn this social experience into elements of their personal experience and intellectual development.

A concept assimilated by man becomes an image, but a special image: abstract and generalized. Indeed, one can think in triangles without imagining any specific object associated with the concept. In principle, it is impossible to clearly express the concept: any image is an image of a certain object, this image, of course, contains important properties.

L.S. Vygotsky was the first to introduce into psychology the division of concepts into scientific and non-scientific - "everyday", at the same time he meant not the content of the concepts to be mastered, but the way of mastering them. The child finds a system of concepts formed in society. Assimilation of this system always occurs with the help of adults. Before systematic teaching at school, adults do not do special work on the formation of concepts in children. They are usually limited to showing whether the child correctly or incorrectly associates the object with the corresponding concept. As a result, the child learns concepts through "trial and error". At the same time, in some cases, orientation actually occurs according to insignificant features, but due to their combination with important ones in objects, it turns out to be correct within certain limits. In others, orientation to vital signs occurs, but they remain unconscious. It is in this unconsciousness that L.S. Vygotsky saw the essential properties and distinctive features of worldly concepts. Such acquisition of concepts does not reflect all aspects of the unique human way of acquiring new knowledge. This is a completely different matter.

L.S. Vygotsky, when a child enters school, the learning process includes a transition from the spontaneous direction of the child's activity to a purposeful, organized activity. He said that the concepts formed by the child at school, their acquisition is characterized by the beginning of knowing the important features of the concept, which is achieved by introducing the definition. According to L.S. Vygotsky, he sees the unique features of scientific concepts in understanding their important features. In his opinion, this way allows the child to act voluntarily and consciously with the concept in the future.

In the works of Vygotsky, the problem of the connection between the role of maturity and learning in the development of the child's higher mental functions is considered in detail. Thus, he formulated the most important principle, according to which the preservation and

timely maturation of brain structures is necessary, but not sufficient, for the development of higher mental functions. The main source of this development is the changing social environment, and to describe it, Vygotsky introduced the term social situation of development, which is "the specific, age-specific, exclusive, or "specific and unrepeatable relations, primarily social". It is this relationship that determines the direction of development of the child's psyche at a certain age.

Vygotsky proposed a new periodicity of human life based on the alternation of periods of stable development and crises. Crises are characterized by revolutionary changes, their criterion is the emergence of neoplasms. According to Vygotsky, the cause of the psychological crisis is the growing gap between the child's developing psyche and the unchanging social situation of development, and the normal crisis is aimed at reconstructing this situation.

Actions based on concepts open up a wide range of "transfer" possibilities, which greatly facilitates and shortens the path of formation of all subsequent concepts. In the formation of scientific concepts, such a direction of the process of mastering concepts should be characteristic. Unlike the acquisition of everyday concepts, it proceeds in a controlled, scientifically organized manner.

References:

1. Nishonova Z.T, G.Alimova "Bolalar psixologiyasi va uni o'qitish metodikasi" Toshkent-2003 yil
2. Sharofitdinov, A. (2022). OILADA SIBLING MAQOMI MUNOSABATLARINING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании, 2(3).
3. Sharafitdinov Abdulla XXX, Soyimnazarov Navro'zbek Baxtiyor ugli, Nishonov Muhammadali Narimon ugli. Characteristics of Emotional Intelligence in Managers Volume: 01 Issue: 10 | Oct-2022
4. Sharafitdinov Abdulla XXX, Soyimnazarov Navro'zbek Baxtiyor ugli, (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CONCEPT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 7, 71-75
5. XXX, Sharafitdinov Abdulla. "CHARACTERISTICS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN MANAGERS." European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development 8 (2022): 22-25.
6. Abdulla Sharofitdinov, Navro'zbek Soyimnazarov, [HISSIIY BEQARORLIK VA UNI OLDINI OLISHNING PSIXOLOGIK USULLARI](#), [Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании: Том 3 № 1 \(2023\)](#)
7. Rashidova G. G. Socio Cultural Approach as a Modern Direction of Teacher
8. Training // International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding.
9. 2021. – T. 8. – No. 8. – С. 169-172.
10. Sharofitdinov, A., & Soyimnazarov, N. (2023). RAHBARLARDA EMOTSIONAL NAZORAT VA O'Z-O'ZINI ANGLASH. Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании, 3(1).

11. Rashidova G. G. INTERPRETATION AND INTERDEPENDENCE OF THE CONCEPTS OF «COMPETENT» AND «COMPETENCE» //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2021. – №. 8. – С. 83-89.
12. Sharofitdinov, A., & Soyimnazarov, N. (2023). BOSHQARUVCHI SHAXSIDA EMOTSIONAL INTELLEKTNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI. Журнал Педагогики и психологии в современном образовании, 3(1).
13. Ergashevich, Y. S. (2022). KIBERHUJUMLARDAN HIMOYALASHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 46-49.
14. Ergashevich, Y. S. (2022). Psychology of modern leadership as an important phenomenon of effective management". Intenational Journal of Early Childhood Special Education ISSN, 1308-5581.
15. Sattorova Mahliyo Burxanovna. (2022). TA'LIM JARAYONIDA PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 436–440.